

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Staneart**FIRST NAME:** Steve**PROGRAM CODE:** MCCT**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
2. The Turabian Style (libraryguides.bennett.edu, n.d.)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Zotero (Zotero.org, n.d.)
6. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
7. Defining the Question (EUCLID 2019, 6)

ROOKIE WRITING ATTEMPT

1) INTRODUCTION

Anytime one learns a new skill, the first application of that skill is fraught with fear and trembling. Certainly, this is the case when learning a new style of writing. I had not even heard of “Turabian style” (EUCLID 2019, 1). I am somewhat familiar with Chicago style from which Turabian style citations are derived and have written in that style on several occasions. Perhaps this is to my detriment, in that knowing how to get close is not the same as knowing how to get it right. Nevertheless, I have been impressed by the approach to teaching the new style, the use of technology as well as classical comparisons. I have also been amazed at the Zotero application and look forward to using it frequently and effectively to fill my papers with appropriate and adequate sources. In this short response paper, I will highlight lessons learned from the ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1 and other resources.

2) PLAGIARISM

In academic circles, plagiarism is a mortal sin for a variety of good reasons that I will outline below; more than a simple *faux pa*, its existence in any academic work is a fatal blunder that renders the work anathema to all who read it.

a) Plagiarism is theft

When an author renders a literary work to a publisher, be that a commercial publishing house, an institution, or a peer reviewed journal, he or she owns that intellectual property. In the case of an academic, his/her intellectual property has real value. It was bought and paid for by the granting of a degree that the author holds. When his/her intellectual property is taken without citation, it robs him/her of the value of that knowledge. More than simply denying him the satisfaction of esteem given, it denies the worth of the author's work; worth that can be valued in dollars and cents based on the monetary value of the degree that the author holds, and the increase in value of the publication as recorded in the various online sites that catalog such assets.

b) Plagiarism is fraud

According to Investopedia, "Fraud is an intentionally deceptive action designed to provide the perpetrator with an unlawful gain" (www.investopedia.com, n.d.). The online article goes on to use such words as "unethical" and "deceitful." When an article is proffered neglecting to cite work, the contents of the article are by default represented as the original thought of the author. In addition to stealing the work from the original author, the effect is to prop up the perpetrator of the plagiarism in ways he or she has not earned. A much better course is to adequately cite works as they are used, giving credit where credit is due.

c) Appropriate citing

"A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers" (EUCLID 2019, 2). One cannot simply avoid plagiarism by neglecting the use of sources, writing entire papers in one's own words. We stand on the shoulders of those who have gone before us, adding weight to our own thoughts by showing how they are consistent with, and built upon the already affirmed thoughts of other learned individuals. These former works must be used and must be referenced. There are many and varied ways of citing. Different disciplines employ a variety of styles. The Modern Language Association uses MLA, the American Psychological Association is APA, and our own Euclid University has several approved citation methods mentioned by Dr. Cleenewerck in his instructional video.

3) THE TURABIAN STYLE

"The Chicago and Turabian Styles, published by the University of Chicago Press, commonly are used for undergraduate History, Philosophy, Political Science, and Religious Studies, as well as other disciplines" (libraryguides.bennett.edu, n.d.). This style fits very well with the Comparative Christian Theologies degree I am pursuing. The Turabian style is an outgrowth of the popular Chicago style of citation, which is used in

most books written for the humanities and is a style I have employed on several occasions in writing for my employer, The Salvation Army. In-text citations include the name of the author, the date of the publication and the page of the reference. Footnotes show the first line indented, with subsequent lines in the entry at the left margin, while in a bibliography, the first line begins flush with the left margin, with subsequent lines indented. While I will admit I struggle with consistency, I understand the importance of accurately citing sources. Not only does the uniformity help when my reader wants to gain further knowledge, but sloppy presentations make a reader doubt the overall quality of the work.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

As I read through the coursepack, listened to the assigned videos, and looked up the associated websites and applications, I was struck by how important it is that an international learning institution like Euclid is serious in formatting issues. I have spent most of my adult life in the United States, and all my education, from grammar school through my undergraduate degree, employing the use of American style English by default. I can imagine how difficult many of my cohorts would find learning, not just a new way of citing, but new and unfamiliar forms of syntax and punctuation. In this vein, my level of respect for those who would choose such a venture is heightened, and my decision to pursue an international degree is affirmed. Also affirmed is my confidence in EUCLID.

5) ZOTERO

My first look at Zotero (Zotero.org, n.d.) was one of awe. I was nothing short of amazed by this tool that allows me to catalogue sources, go back to them without having to look them up again, and have the application help me to correctly cite the source, both in-text and in the bibliography. My application of the application, however, was a little more troubled. It is not as user friendly as I had hoped it might be, but I came away from the process with a functional knowledge that I am sure will get better with practice.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

The majority of my adult life I have made my living in communications, preaching, teaching, writing, public relations, etc. Of course, I have used Latin abbreviations (as I just did in the previous sentence) thoughtlessly. Most of the Latin shorthand expressed in this lesson are second nature. The benefit I found from this study is one of context. I have now a deeper appreciation for what they are and what they mean, as well as a better understanding of how they are appropriately used in an academic format.

7) DEFINING THE QUESTION

When writing in more informal styles, as I have for most of my career, defining the question was less important. Magazines would publish my articles as much for their poetic value as their prose. Though the art of writing is no less important in academic pursuits, the point of the article is more important. I must remember to clearly define the question. “Answering the essay’s question or task is central” (EUCLID 2019, 6).

8) CONCLUSION

Old dogs are notorious for being unable to learn new tricks, or so the well-worn American cliché goes. As a more seasoned learner, I will freely admit that trying on a new way of doing things is not as easy as it once was. Though I have used the American Psychological Association (APA) format before and the Chicago style, I had not heretofore heard of, much less employed the Turabian style of citation. I truly appreciate Zotero, and the other technologies I was introduced to in this course but will admit struggling a bit use them. But this is my maiden voyage, my rookie paper. I will get better at using the tools as time goes on. The first part of my first course showed an amazing level of sophistication in dealing with internet and distance learning tools, and an ability to engage the learner across language and cultural boundaries. It is an auspicious start. I cannot wait for assignment number two.

REFERENCES

Chen, James. “Fraud Definition.” Investopedia. Investopedia, April 9, 2021.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/fraud.asp>.

“Chicago/Turabian Style.” Holgate Library Research Guides. Accessed April 12, 2021.
<http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

“Your Personal research Assistant.” Zotero. Accessed April 12, 2021.
<https://www.zotero.org/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.